

I.FAST

Innovation Fostering in Accelerator Science and Technology

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NOTE - 002

Report of I.FAST Workshop on Beam Diagnostics and Dynamics in Ultra-low Emittance Ring

WP 7 Task 7.2

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ABSTRACT

The I.FAST workshop on beam diagnostics and dynamics in ultra-low emittance ring took place from the 25th to 29th of April 2022 organised by KIT as a video conference style due to the pandemic situation. The participants and organisers overcame this challenge and the workshop had 20 scientific presentations from 26 institutes and universities and 12 countries. The workshop was a great success to network the accelerator community, especially in the field of beam diagnostics and dynamics. This document reports the aim of the workshop, the scientific organisation and program including the abstracts of the presentations, which are published on the following Indigo website: <https://indico.scc.kit.edu/event/2592/>

REPORT OF I.FAST WORKSHOP ON BEAM DIAGNOSTICS AND DYNAMICS IN ULTRA-LOW EMITTANCE RING

I.FAST Consortium, 2022/2023

For more information on I.FAST, its partners and contributors please see <https://ifast-project.eu/>

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Delivery Slip

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DIAGNOSTICS AND DYNAMICS IN ULTRA-LOW
EMITTANCE RING**

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1. Introduction

Today, in Europe and the world, several projects for ring-based synchrotron light sources are going on, aiming to generate high-brilliance synchrotron light by ultra-low emittance beams. One of the critical issues for such a high-quality beam is the beam dynamics that handle the beam optics and realise the ultra-low emittance beam by keeping sufficient beam stability by the optics design. On the other hand, it is also essential to precisely evaluate the beam quality and stability for such a high-quality beam by beam diagnostics. The workshop reported here aimed to prepare the opportunity to discuss the beam dynamics and diagnostics for the ultra-low emittance and high-quality beam and share the possibilities and requests from both sides.

The workshop was organised at Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT) by the Institute for Beam Physics and Technology (IBPT) with a digital (online) style, considering the Covid19 pandemic situation worldwide. Due to the participation worldwide, all scientific programs took place for five days in the afternoon in Central European Time. Despite the unusual conditions due to the pandemic, the workshop was a great success, with 81 registered participants from 26 institutes and universities and 12 countries and 20 scientific presentations. It was noticeable that several discussions happened over the session categories during the workshop, showing that the workshop reach the goal and could contribute to networking between the participants dedicated to beam dynamics and diagnostics worldwide.

In the following, we briefly summarised the workshop information, including the workshop program, presentation list, registered participants list and workshop organisation.

2. Content

2.1 SCIENTIFIC SESSIONS

The workshop had the following eight scientific sessions:

- Overview session
- Transverse single-particle dynamics
- Transverse beam diagnostics
- Longitudinal beam dynamics
- Beam dynamics on collective effects
- Beam dynamics on beam injection
- Long-term stability problem
- Beam diagnostics and machine learning

On the first day, the first two sessions were mainly focused on comprehensive topics of beam diagnostics and beam dynamics on ultra-low emittance rings, which orientated the following sessions about transverse beam diagnostics. The combination of beam dynamics and diagnostics sessions was a noteworthy characteristic of this workshop. The same combination was organised for longitudinal beam dynamics and diagnostics on the second day, beam dynamics and diagnostics on collective effects on the third day, and beam dynamics and diagnostics on beam injection on the fourth day.

The last day of the workshop had two separate sessions, which were on long-term stability problems, and beam diagnostics and machine learning. The former session focused on the stability problems in low-emittance rings, which will be considered serious in future ultra-low-emittance rings. The latter session treated methods which have been coming nowadays.

2.2 PRESENTATIONS LIST

- Day One (25/04)

Session	Presentation and Presenter	Session Chair
Open session 1	Greetings Anke-Susanne Müller (KIT)	Akira Mochihashi (KIT)
Open session 2	Introduction KIT, KARA, and FLUTE Bastian Härer (KIT)	
Open session 3	Information Akira Mochihashi (KIT)	
Overview session	Diagnostics Requirements for Ultra-Low Emittance Rings Volker Schlott (PSI)	Bastian Härer (KIT)
Session 1-1 Transverse single particle dynamics 1	Optimization of sextupole magnetic fields at the SPring-8 storage ring Yoshito Shimosaki (KEK)	Bastian Härer (KIT)

Session 1-2 Transverse beam diagnostics 1	Transverse beam diagnostics at MAX IV Åke Andersson (MAX IV)	
Session 1-3 Transverse beam diagnostics 2	Transverse beam size diagnostics and some applications to storage ring operation and beam studies at the ESRF Friederike Ewald (ESRF)	Gero Kube (DESY)
Session 1-4 Transverse beam diagnostics 3	Photon beam diagnostics for SOLEIL upgrade project Marie Labat (SOLEIL)	
Session 1-5 Transverse beam diagnostics 4	Beam Position Monitors and Orbit Feedback for Low Emittance Rings Nicolas Hubert (SOLEIL)	

- Day Two (26/04)

Session	Presentation and Presenter	Session Chair
Session 2-1 Longitudinal beam dynamics 1	Longitudinal beam dynamics in ultra-low emittance rings Francis J. Cullinan (MAX-IV)	Markus Schwarz (KIT)
Session 2-2 Longitudinal beam diagnostics 1	Turn-by-turn and bunch-by-bunch diagnostic developments at KIT Johannes Steinmann (KIT)	
Session 2-3 Longitudinal beam diagnostics 2	Electron-bunch dynamics during the micro-bunching instability: third-generation & low-emittance configuration Clément Evain (Lille University)	

- Day Three (27/04)

Session	Presentation and Presenter	Session Chair
Session 3-1 Beam dynamics on collective effects 1	Harmonic cavity studies for the SOLEIL Upgrade Alexis Gamelin (SOLEIL)	Ryutaro Nagaoka (SOLEIL)
Session 3-2 Beam dynamics on collective effects 2	Implementation and Collective Effects during Negative Momentum Compaction Operation at KARA Patrick Schreiber (KIT)	
Session 3-3 Beam diagnostics on collective effects 1	Diagnosing collective effects in the MAX IV storage rings Miriam Brosi (MAX-IV)	Edmund Blomley (KIT)
Session 3-4 Beam diagnostics on collective effects 2	Overview of the Longitudinal and Transverse Bunch by Bunch Feedback at DAFNE Giovanni Franzini (INFN)	

- Day Four (28/04)

Session	Presentation and Presenter	Session Chair
Session 4-1	Beam dynamics on beam injection	Michael Boege (PSI)

Beam dynamics on beam injection 1	Masamitsu Aiba (PSI)	
Session 4-2 Beam diagnostics on beam injection 1	Diagnosics and beam dynamics in the Bessy II Booster Synchrotron Meghan Jill McAteer (HZB)	
Session 4-3 Beam diagnostics on beam injection 2	An improvised beam diagnostics system for the cSTART storage ring Dima El Khechen (KIT)	

- Day Five (29/04)

Session	Presentation and Presenter	Session Chair
Session 5-1 Long term stability problem 1	Beam stability at the MAX IV storage rings Jonas Breunlin (MAX-IV)	Akira Mochihashi (KIT)
Session 5-2 Long term stability problem 2	Investigation of characteristics and sources of beam orbit instabilities in modern light sources Sukho Kongtawong (Stony Brook University)	
Session 6-1 Beam diagnostics and machine learning 1	Virtual diagnostics for high brightness particle accelerators Claudio Emma (SLAC)	Pedro Fernandes Tavares (MAX-IV)
Session 6-2 Beam diagnostics and machine learning 2	Machine learning to control and predict beam properties Andrea Santamaria Garcia (KIT)	

2.3 PARTICIPANT LIST

The participant list is shown in the following, where the names of the registered participants are listed with alphabetic order. The number of the registered participants amounted to 81 people in total.

Last Name	First Name	Affiliation
Abo-Bakr	Michael	Helmholtz-Zentrum Berlin (HZB)
Ahmadi	Esmail	ILSF
Andersson	Åke	MAX IV Laboratory / Lund University
Apollonio	Marco	MAX IV
Arlandoo	Michael	Helmholtz-Zentrum Berlin
Bassi	Gabriele	Brookhaven National Laboratory
Bettoni	Simona	Paul Scherrer Institut
Blednykh	Alexei	BNL/EIC
Bobb	Lorraine	Diamond Light Source
Boege	Michael	Paul Scherrer Institut
Brosi	Miriam	MAX IV
Bründermann	Erik	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT) - IBPT
Ca	Manuel	Instrumentation Technologies d.o.o.
Caselle	Michele	
Cullinan	Francis	MAX IV Laboratory
Dastan	Sara	Elettra Sincrotron Trieste
Eichler	Annika	DESY
Emma	Claudio	SLAC
Evain	Clément	Lille University/PhLAM Laboratory
Ewald	Friederike	ESRF
Ferrentino	Vittorio	
Fielder	Richard	Diamond Light Source
Gamelin	Alexis	Synchrotron SOLEIL
Gassner	David	BNL

Goslowski	Paul	Helmholtz-Zentrum Berlin, BESSY II, MLS
Haerer	Bastian	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT)
He	Ping	IHEP
Hidaka	Yoshiteru	NSLS-II
hosaka	masahito	National Synchrotron Radiation Laboratory, University of Science and Technology of China
Houghton	Claire	Diamond Light Source
HUBERT	Nicolas	Synchrotron SOLEIL
Hwang	Ji-Gwang	Helmholtz-Zentrum Berlin
Ishida	Takashi	Nagoya University
Jochim	Leyla	Institute for Beam Physics and Technolgy (IBPT)
Jummunt	Siriwan	Synchrotron Light Research Institute (SLRI)
Juntong	Nawin	Synchrotron Light Research Institute
Kallestrup	Jonas	Diamond Light Source
Karataev	Pavel	Royal Holloway, University of London
Kongtawong	Sukho	stony brook university
Krecic	Stefano	Elettra Sincrotron Trieste
Kube	Gero	Deutsches Elektronen-Synchrotron (DESY)
Kuske	Bettina	HZB
Kuske	Peter	Helmholtz-Zentrum Berlin
Kötter	Stephan-Robert	KIT IBPT
Labat	Marie	SOLEIL
Li	Ji	Helmholtz-Zentrum berlin
Lonza	Marco	Elettra Sincrotrone Trieste
Malygin	Anton	KIT
Manukyan	Koryun	Elettra Sincrotrone Trieste
Martin	Ian	Diamond Light Source
McAteer	Meghan	Helmholtz-Zentrum Berlin
Mirza	Sajjad Hussain	MSK, DESY, Hamburg

Mochihashi	Akira	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology
Morgan	Alun	Diamond Light Source
Müller	Anke-Susanne	KIT
Nadolski	Laurent	Synchrotron SOLEIL
Olsson	Teresia	Diamond Light Source
Pfeiffer	Sven	DESY
Preston	Shaun	Diamond Light Source
Pulampong	Thapakron	SLRI
Ries	Markus	Helmholtz-Zentrum Berlin
Rose	Austen	Diamond Light Source Ltd
Ruprecht	Robert	KIT
Salehi Derakhtanjani	Elham	UVSOR synchrotron facility, IMS
Santamaria Garcia	Andrea	KIT
Schiwietz	Gregor	BESSY II, HZB
Schlott	Volker	Paul Scherrer Institut
Schreiber	Patrick	KIT
Schuh	Marcel	KIT
Schwarz	Markus	KIT
Shaftan	Timur	Brookhaven National Laboratory
Shi	Liangliang	HZB
Steinmann	Johannes	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology
Wang	Faya	slac national accelerator lab
wang	jiuqing	Institute of High Energy Physics, CAS
Wang	Siwei	Diamond Light Source
Wawrzyniak	Adriana	SOLARIS
Wilkes	Seb	The University of Oxford
Wittenburg	Kay	DESY
Xu	Haisheng	IHEP, CAS, Beijing, China
Yang	Xi	BNL

2.4 SCIENTIFIC PROGRAM COMMITTEE

The member of the scientific program committee was organised with experts in the field of accelerator physics and technology, especially related to beam diagnostics. The scientific program committee nominated presenters on the workshop based on the session categories.

Name	Organization
Volker Schlott	PSI
Pedro Fernandes Tavares	Max-Lab
Peter Kuske	HZB
Marica Biagini	INFN
Nicolas Hubert	SOLEIL
Guenther Rehm	HZB
Holger Schlarb	DESY
Lorraine Bobb	Diamond
Angeles Faus-Golfe	IJCLab, Orsay
Deepa Angal-Kalinin	ASTeC

3. Presentations Abstracts

Overview session: *Volker Schlott (PSI)*

Diagnostics Requirements for Ultra-Low Emittance Rings

The new generation of diffraction-limited light sources, based on ultra-low emittance storage rings pose several more stringent requirements on beam diagnostics systems. This talk provides an overview of developments, which aim for highest beam stability and the measurement of ultra-low emittance beams.

Session 1-1 Transverse beam dynamics: *Yoshito Shimosaki (KEK)*

Optimization of sextupole magnetic fields at the SPring-8 storage ring

In a low emittance ring, an optimization of the sextupole magnetic fields is indispensable for the sufficient beam injection and the long beam lifetime. At the SPring-8 storage ring, the beam dynamic issues caused by sextupole fields, such as the nonlinear resonances and the amplitude dependent tune shifts, were examined by using the analysis based on the Hamiltonian and the tracking code CETRA [1]. The sextupole coefficients optimized for the beam injection were adopted to the machine, and the improvement of the injection efficiency was experimentally confirmed. The beam dynamic phenomena observed with the turn-by-turn monitors well represented the tracking results. These results will be presented in detail.

[1] J. Schimizu, et al., Proc. of 13th Symp. on Accel. Sci. and Tech. Osaka, Japan (2001), pp.80-82.

Session 1-2 Transverse beam diagnostics 1: *Åke Andersson (MAX IV)*

Transverse beam diagnostics at MAX IV

The transverse beam diagnostics for the fourth-generation 3 GeV storage ring at MAX IV Laboratory, Lund University, is described in some detail. We focus on the challenges of monitoring rms beam sizes in the range of five to thirty microns, using visible and near-visible synchrotron radiation. Simultaneous use of two diagnostic beam lines allows for both emittance and energy spread determination.

Session 1-3 Transverse beam diagnostics 2: *Friederike Ewald (ESRF)*

Transverse beam size diagnostics and some applications to storage ring operation and beam studies at the ESRF

Since the upgrade of the ESRF storage ring to a small emittance lattice, the transverse beam profile of the stored electron beam reaches very low values, and its measurement becomes therefore challenging. At the ESRF we continue to use the X-ray pinhole as regular beam size monitor. Development of other techniques with the potential of high resolution is ongoing. The transverse profile (or emittance) diagnostics has several applications to beam studies and optimization of operation parameters, which will also be presented here.

Session 1-4 Transverse beam diagnostics 3: *Marie Labat (SOLEIL)*

Photon beam diagnostics for SOLEIL upgrade project

SOLEIL is planning an upgrade of its storage ring in order to increase the photon beam brightness for users by reducing the electron beam transverse emittance. We present here the strategy in terms of diagnostics for electron beam size measurements. Due to the dramatic reduction of the beam sizes indeed, the machine diagnostics will also have to be updated and/or re-designed. We will also present on-going works to prepare those next generation diagnostics.

Session 1-5 Transverse beam diagnostics 4: *Nicolas Hubert (SOLEIL)*

Beam Position Monitors and Orbit Feedback for Low Emittance Rings

The beam size reduction in the low emittance rings associated to the miniaturization of the vacuum chamber conduct to tight requirements for the beam position monitoring system. The long-term stability is particularly challenging. Ongoing mechanical and electronic designs envisioned to meet those specifications are presented. In addition, the performances of the future orbit feedback system will also be improved by (in particular) increasing the closed loop bandwidth conducting to a larger efficiency range. Consequences on the architecture of the system and the involved electronics latencies are also discussed.

Session 2-1 Longitudinal beam dynamics 1: *Francis J. Cullinan (MAX IV)*

Longitudinal beam dynamics in ultra-low emittance rings

A key feature of ultra-low emittance storage rings is the need for bunch lengthening to prevent emittance degradation from intra-beam scattering and/or to improve the Touschek beam lifetime. This is typically solved using Landau cavities operating at a harmonic of the main RF. These may be actively powered through the use of additional RF transmitters or passively driven by the beam itself. Using the MAX IV 3 GeV ring as an example, the most important considerations in the design and operation of these double-RF systems are reviewed from a beam-dynamics perspective. Potential issues and possible mitigations are identified. Finally, the option of adding RF cavities at additional higher harmonics, with the goal of lengthening the bunches even further, is discussed.

Session 2-2 Longitudinal beam diagnostics 1: *Johannes Steinmann (KIT)*

Turn-by-turn and bunch-by-bunch diagnostic developments at KIT

Novel accelerators require unprecedented accuracy and speed in electron bunch diagnostics. The goal to continuously measure the 6D phase space of every bunch at each turn will enable novel real time analysis and feedback control systems. In this contribution we focus on the latest advances at KIT to measure the longitudinal phase space and to set up new machine learning based feedback systems.

Session 2-3 Longitudinal beam diagnostics 2: *Clément Evain (Lille University)*

Electron-bunch dynamics during the micro-bunching instability: third-generation & low-emittance configuration

The Coherent Synchrotron Radiation (CSR) instability (or microbunching instability) is a general process that occurs in accelerators-based light sources, when the electron bunch peak current is sufficiently high. Due to the interaction of the electrons with their own radiation, micro-structures spontaneously appear in the longitudinal profile of the bunch, usually with a bursting behavior. We will present (mainly) studies from a collaboration between Synchrotron SOLEIL and the PhLAM laboratory, on the dynamics of an electron bunch during this instability. We will first focus on the comparison between numerical results (using the Vlasov-Fokker-Planck equation), and ultrafast measurements (using the so-called time-stretch electro-optic sampling technique) in the context of the present configuration of Synchrotron SOLEIL. The second part will be dedicated to numerical studies of the bunch dynamics in the context of the low-emittance configuration of the future upgrade of Synchrotron SOLEIL.

Session 3-1 Beam dynamics on collective effects 1: *Alexis Gamelin (SOLEIL)*

Harmonic cavity studies for the SOLEIL Upgrade

In 4th generation low emittance synchrotron light sources, harmonic cavities are critical components needed to reach the required performance. However, RF systems with harmonic cavities are limited by their own set of instabilities: the 'slow-moving transient instability' can prevent the RF system from reaching the flat potential conditions, hence limiting the maximum bunch lengthening, the AC Robinson sets a limit on the low beam current operation and the HOM coupled bunch instability threshold can be lower as compared to the single RF case, despite the added Landau damping. Here we report how these instabilities could impact the performance and influence the choice between different technologies and harmonic (3rd and 4th) for the SOLEIL Upgrade.

Session 3-2 Beam dynamics on collective effects 2: *Patrick Schreiber (KIT)*

Implementation and Collective Effects during Negative Momentum Compaction Operation at KARA

For future low-emittance synchrotron light sources new operation modes are of interest. One such mode uses a negative momentum compaction factor for the possibility of an increased dynamic aperture. Therefore, operation with such an optics has been implemented and is under investigation at the Karlsruhe Research Accelerator (KARA). Using a variety of high-performance beam diagnostics systems various studies of collective effects, such as the current dependent bunch length and the equivalent of the micro-bunching instability, have been performed. This contribution will present the implementation and first results on the studies of collective effects in the negative momentum compaction factor regime at KARA.

Session 3-3 Beam diagnostics on collective effects 1: *Miriam Brosi (MAX IV)*

Diagnosing collective effects in the MAX IV storage rings

The fourth-generation 3 GeV storage-ring at the MAX IV light source, as any ultra-low emittance machine, is sensitive to collective effects. A manifold combination of diagnostic setups is a valuable tool to investigate as well as monitor the impact and consequences of these collective effects at different time scales, from static bunch profiles and slowly oscillating instabilities to fast dynamics turn-by-turn. For example, the newly installed streak cameras at the diagnostic beamlines of the 1.5 GeV and 3 GeV rings are able to perform both slow and accurate measurements as well as fast turn-by-turn measurements of single and multiple bunches in various operation modes of the storage rings. This contribution will present their setup, a small discussion of the performed analysis and some examples of first measurements conducted in combination with other diagnostic tools for the study of collective effects.

Session 3-4 Beam diagnostics on collective effects 2: *Giovanni Franzini (INFN)*

Overview of the Longitudinal and Transverse Bunch by Bunch Feedback at DAFNE

DAFNE is an electron-positron collider in operation at LNF-INFN for physics experiments since 1999. It produces e^+/e^- collisions at a center of mass energy of 1.02 GeV. Up to 120 bunches, with a total average current in the range of 1A/2A are stored in two 97 m main rings and collide in the interaction region, where a detector for the SIDDARTHA-2 experiment is currently installed. In order to reduce coupled-bunch instabilities bunch-by bunch feedbacks were installed since the start of operations and upgraded during the last two decades. A total of three feedbacks are used per ring (e^+/e^-). One for the longitudinal motion of the particles, two for the transversal motion (vertical and horizontal). Since its first runs, DAFNE has always shown dynamic behaviour strongly dependent on the bunch-by-bunch feedback. The latter is in fact critical in order to achieve the aforementioned values of currents. An overview of the feedback systems will be presented, as well as the most recent measurements and results obtained.

Session 4-1 Beam dynamics on beam injection 1: *Masamitsu Aiba (PSI)*

Beam dynamics on beam injection

Top-up injection is prerequisite to maximize the performance and stability of the lepton collider and the light source. It is one of challenges for the new generation light source, where the machine aperture is rather limited: the low emittance lattice tends to make the dynamics aperture smaller while insertion devices with smaller aperture may realize higher photon beam performance. In this presentation, the beam dynamics relevant to beam injection are discussed together with the beam diagnostics that are necessary during the injection tuning. The talk will cover the first beam injection in the commissioning as well as the injection tuning in the regular operation.

Session 4-2 Beam diagnostics on beam injection 1: *Meghan Jill McAteer (HZB)*

Beam dynamics on beam injection

The Bessy II Booster is a fast-ramping synchrotron which has been reliably delivering beam to the BII storage ring for several decades. Recently, new instrumentation has been installed and commissioned, including a bunch-by-bunch feedback system and a turn-by-turn beam position measurement system. These upgrades allow for further improvements in the performance of the machine, as well as measurement and control of beam dynamics parameters to an extent that was not previously possible with the available instrumentation. Here we discuss some considerations for beam control and diagnostics which are specific to fast-ramping machines, and we present the results of various beam dynamics measurements and corrections in the Booster, such as controlling the closed orbit distortion, transverse and longitudinal tunes, and chromaticity throughout the acceleration ramp.

Session 4-3 Beam diagnostics on beam injection 2: *Dima El Khechen (KIT)*

An improvised beam diagnostics system for the cSTART storage ring

In the framework of the project cSTART (compact Storage Ring for Accelerator Research and Technology), which is being realized at Karlsruhe Institute for Technology (KIT), a Very Large Acceptance compact Storage Ring (VLA-cSR) is planned to study the injection and the storage of 50 MeV, ultra-short (sub-ps) or LPA-like (laser plasma accelerator) electron bunches. For such a storage ring, where a single bunch with a relatively wide range of bunch charge (1-1000 pC) and energy spread (10^{-4} to 10^{-2}) will circulate at a relatively high revolution frequency (about 7 MHz), the choice of beam diagnostics is a challenge. In this talk, we would like to discuss possible beam diagnostics systems, mainly beam position monitors, and beam loss monitors which are essential to guarantee a smooth injected/stored beam (and the beam alignment inside) in the cSTART storage ring. Moreover, we will address the underlying challenges of the chosen diagnostics elements in the VLA-cSR and report on the planned tests in the booster synchrotron of KARA which should help us forecast the behavior of such elements in cSTART.

Session 5-1 Long term stability problem 1: *Jonas Breunlin (MAX IV)*

Beam stability at the MAX IV storage rings

The MAX IV Laboratory, inaugurated in 2016, hosts a 3 GeV ring ultra-low emittance storage ring, a 1.5 GeV storage ring and a linear accelerator driven Short Pulse Facility. A Stability Task Force has been assigned to ensure the delivery of stable beams to MAX IV users since early on in the design phase of the laboratory and is continuing its work in an ongoing and multi-disciplinary effort. Measurements of the electron beam stability resulting from the passive stabilization approach taken for the two storage rings will be presented, as well as figures of beam stability with the Fast Orbit Feedback system in operation. Each ID beamline in the 3 GeV storage ring is equipped with a pair photon beam position monitors that are currently used to complement the electron beam position monitors. In the light of the city development around the MAX IV campus, maintaining the good mechanical stability of the laboratory has to be seen as an ongoing effort. A number of studies are being performed to identify possible risks and to decide where measures need to be taken.

Session 5-2 Long term stability problem 2: *Sukho Kongtawong (Storony Brook University)*

Investigation of characteristics and sources of beam orbit instabilities in modern light sources

We discuss the analysis and methodologies to characterize the electron beam instabilities in NSLS-II and other storage rings. First, we introduce the experimental methods and the analytic models that we implemented to characterize spectra of the electron beam orbit instabilities. Then we discuss the theoretical analysis and experiments to identify the noise sources, as well as accomplishments in stabilizing the beam by suppressing the noise from the sources. In particular, the BPM data indicated the dominant spectral noise range is located within 100 Hz, which was found to be excited by the water-cooling system. We have also detected and analyzed noise components from other ring subsystems such as RF and top-off injection. We present a development of an application for live monitoring of beam instabilities, which was implemented on the NSLS-II storage ring to monitor real-time orbit performance during beam operations. Finally, we present our studies on integral stability of X-ray beam along 120 m long Hard X-ray Nanoprobe beamline that enables microscopy experiments with the resolution of 10 nm. As a part of the presentation, we will share experience from other accelerator facilities in solving stability problems to increase the beam brightness.

Session 6-1 Beam diagnostics and machine learning 1: *Claudio Emma (SLAC)*

Virtual diagnostics for high brightness particle accelerators

Virtual diagnostics are computational tools which predict the output of measurement devices. They are especially useful when they predict the output of intercepting diagnostics which otherwise affect the ability to simultaneously measure e-beam properties and use the beams for experiments. In this talk I will report on the application of machine learning-based virtual diagnostics for predicting the longitudinal phase space (LPS) of high brightness beams. I will discuss the use of such ML-diagnostic for prediction as well as to tune accelerator settings to generate desired LPS profiles. Finally, I will discuss recent work in using ML based surrogate modeling and optimization applicable for emittance minimization in linacs and storage rings.

Session 6-2 Beam diagnostics and machine learning 2: *Andrea Santamaria Garcia (KIT)*

Machine learning to control and predict beam properties

Accelerators are one of the most complex machines in the world, where their manual tuning is a laborious process even for experienced operators. Humans can only act on a few parameters simultaneously and operate on a narrow set of timescales. Additionally, the relationship between parameters changes depending on external conditions. Due to the high number of parameters required to operate an accelerator and the nonlinear correlation between them, as well as the need for different operation modes and the presence of many non-controllable variables, accelerators are an excellent candidate to benefit from machine learning methods. Moreover, the increased complexity of future accelerators with higher energy, higher brightness, and higher gradients will require advancing the capabilities of accelerator facilities with technologies like machine learning. In this contribution we introduce the different ways in which machine learning can be used in particle accelerators and we present the machine learning activities at KIT.

4. References

All presentation slides which have been published and officially opened are available in the following Indico website. Additional information concerning the workshop is also available in the Indico website.

<https://indico.scc.kit.edu/event/2592/>